

Correlates of Pupil Response and EDA to Dynamic Visual Contents at Phasic Change

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Abstract

Functional Electrodermal Activity (EDA) is mostly associated with central mechanisms which usually play different roles that involve gross movements and affective processes with fine motor control. Pupil dilation is also one of the most well-known physiological measures that can tell a lot about a person's cognitive state, it not only tells of light reflection but a great insight into the cognitive processes of a person based on unconscious thought. This paper integrates these two methods of eliciting the physiological response of a person by integrating the concepts of the two measures, thereby creating an analytical model for accessing both metrics as a form of multimodal physiological assessment of users to dynamic contents of a webpage. The metric is integrated into a touch-sensor pad for recording the input image of the fingers and moisture content detected while involved in a task-allocated session. The two metrics were compared and errors in both physiological attributes were determined. The result shows less error in the contribution of EDA to cognitive stress detection to that of the pupil response and the authenticity of using EDA for gauging the emotional response of users.

Keywords: Electrodermal activity, Pupil measures, Cognitive state, Touch sensor pad, Physiological response, Task performance, Performance and error rate

History

Received: 2nd, June 2022

Revised: 3th, August 2022

Accepted: 6th, September 2022

Published: 8th, January 2023

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1 Introduction

The recent trend in physiological measures shows that the novel non-invasive instrumentation for sympathetic nervous system dynamics using EDA has rapidly gained

some popularity in most experimental procedures. EDA is a measure of the changes in electrical conductance of the skin with a strong correlation to moisture content on skin cursed by task involvement. Some of these tasks are designed to induce a slightly average response from the respondents, and such activities include

dynamic contents of webpages. Dynamic content, often referred to as adaptive content refers to web content that changes based on the behaviour, interests, preferences, and cognition of the user. The contents are usually personalised and adapted based on the data one has about the user and on the access time, the main goal is to deliver an engaging and satisfying online user experience. Dynamic content mostly starts with static content and a classic example is the HTML landing page that changes to display major information that is related to the contents and for the viewer based on location and previous interactions with the website. Different websites have dynamic content in line with static content to personalise their user experience. Some common parts of text content can also be transformed into dynamic content, such as the weather, temperature, user's location, and browsers. They are given as a piece of information that can be immediately used during first-time visits to the website. This paper uses these dynamic content parameters for the basic stimuli used in the method section, the dynamic content is often seen to cause some form of reaction to the physiological readings of respondents. The EDA and pupil measure is one of the major physiological readings that are most responsive to basic dynamic stimulus on webpages, the concept of EDA is also a matter of concision to be taken [5, 18, 11, 16, 36, 23, 22, 19, 20].

2 Literature Review

The concept of EDA is that it is the property of the human body that causes continuous variation in the electrical characteristics of the skin. It has a long history of being known as the skin conductance and sympathetic conductance level (SCL). Recent research [26, 12, 29, 28, 14, 39, 10, 25, 1, 15, 21] has investigated the active and passive electrical properties of the skin by a lot of disciplines which has resulted in an excess of standard electrodermal activity. The standard theory of the EDA states that skin resistance varies with the state of moisture contents from the sweat gland, thus controlled by the sympathetic nervous system (SNS) and it is known as an indicator of psychological and physiological response to stimuli [32, 2, 7, 38, 3, 31]. Research also states that EDA is more complex than it seems and there is a continuous investigation that it could be contradictory in terms of response peak detection only when in a controlled environment [35, 17, 34, 8, 6, 27]. Another physiological response that can be a form of support to EDA is the pupil response which gives a great insight into the cognitive response of a person.

The pupil measure is a physiological response that varies in the size of the pupil through the optic and oculomotor nerves. Pupil constriction is the narrowing of the pupil, which is an indicator of stress and drowsiness, this occurs when the circular muscle is controlled by the parasympathetic nervous system contraction and the radial muscle

relaxes [13, 30, 37, 9, 26]. Pupil dilation is the widening of the pupil and may be caused when the muscle is relaxed and the iris sphincter muscle is relaxed. The resultant responses are caused by different causes from involuntary reflex to light intensity and response to an extensive amount or reaction to a visual stimulus like a change in colour visuals. The latency of the pupil measure i.e. the time it takes for a response to occur increases with age differences [24, 4, 33].

Figure 1: Framework for the multimodal physiological measuring sensor with a touch screen pad for user response measure.

3 Method

The method used in this paper is based on an experimental setup where fifty participants were selected without age restriction, they were asked to sit in front of a Laptop with an embedded webcam that calibrates their eyes to track their eye movements and measure changes in pupil sizes. The initial stage was designing a multimodal physiological sensor (Figure 1) with a touchpad surrounded by magnetic fields that measure the moisture content from a fingertip contact to its surface. The changes in the moisture content detected are then simulated to represent the EDA equivalent of the human body. This is based on a third-order differential equation similar to changes in reaction to stimulus.

The participants were asked to interact with visual dynamic webpages (Figure 2), while their physiological responses were taken. Eye movements are recorded together with other user response data like a mouse click, keypress, and web address and links they visited, these attributes include the mapped fixation on the coordinates of the visual webpages. The pupil size is based on constriction and dilation (i.e. related to stress and the relaxed cognitive state of the user).

The EDA is measured based on tonic and phasic changes and this is determined by the skin conductance level

(Baseline). The latency in the EDA is the time it takes for the response to occur in the readings and is used to determine a stimulus onset. Each participant was simply asked to interact with the dynamic contents on the webpages and was asked to place their fingertips on the touchpad while they interacted with webpage. The EDA is correlated to the moisture content value simulated from the fingertip from the input matrix of the image captured. The temperature at the first point of content also represents the temperature of the skin from the hotness or coldness of the moisture content.

Figure 2: User interaction with a visual stimulus and a multimodal touchpad sensor in front of them.

4 Result

Figure 3 shows the aggregate response of the participants to the dynamic webpage, with pupil dilation and constriction registered as the fixation locations on the webpage. The webpage is an extract of an e-learning page where there are different pictures and text content that often appears in sequence or random order depending on the pages' subtleties. The main task is to search methods of registration by glancing at the page and identifying areas that require user text entries and the nature of the input text field. The nature of the dynamic contents would seem at first confusing and this induces some form of reaction from the participants. Other reactions are seen to appear relaxing when the participant finally has a comprehension of what to do. The fixations on the webpages are seen to overlap each other at some places, the constriction overlapping dilated concentration usually signifies confusion, which is finally replaced by intense concentration as a spatial order of constriction markers on other places on the webpage. The fixation doesn't tell us much about the user response but the physiological correlates (SCR, ST, moisture content, and size in pupil changes) can give a lot more definition about the user's perception and cognition of the dynamic contents.

Figure 3: Aggregate user responses on a dynamic e-learning website.

Figure 4 shows the physiological correlates of user response to dynamic contents, the pupil response is seen to have the same characteristic response behaviour as the SCR and can be differentiated based on its response correlates. The changes in pupil size tend to increase in frequency at a high state of cognition which is similar to an increase in moisture content of the skin (similar to EDA) in reaction to the response to the stimulus. The fingertips image is first detected and moisture content on surface contact is converted to an input parameter which is measured continuously with time. The customised data is seen to be noisy at first reading but the application of a moving average filter can help to smoothen the response reading for a baseline estimate. One can set the parameter level based on tonic and phasic changes. The phasic changes are the spikes that occur in the EDA and pupil response and are usually correlated to sudden reaction to instant reaction to predetermine stimulus effect. The error in EDA and Pupil response is computed from the aggregate response of the participant's data. This is to test the reliability and contribution of the physiological measuring parameters and the inference engine used in the prediction and simulation of the initial data input state.

The response correlates of the physiological response are classified as tonic and phasic changes and this can be complex at some point since there are levels where one can find a flat response, the flat response doesn't signify a no-response state but can be estimated by a certain value that gives meaning to its response state, e.g. the ST is measured based on $30 \times 3.50C$ to synchronise with the EDA and pupil measures; this is also estimated for all the physiological metrics. The error bar in Figure 5, shows

Figure 4: Detected response readings and correlates to dynamic contents on controller evaluator.

the standard deviation and mean error square (MES) of the EDA in terms of the classified response state. The Standard deviation shows an average deviation from the mean response and the tonic and phasic change have an error rate of 0.1% and 0.2% from the mean and greater than the estimated value of 0.05%. The result is feasible and shows the reliability of the model predictions on the user attributes.

Figure 5b indicates the error in detection and performance of the pupil response contributed to the model's routine, the response correlates with the classification based on the dilation and constriction response to stimuli and the related tonic and phasic changes of the EDA. This can be complex at some point like the EDA, since there are levels where we can find a flat response, the flat response doesn't mean no response detected but is estimated as a certain value that gives meaning to the response state. The ST is measured based on $31 \times 50C$ to synchronise with the EDA and pupil measures; this is also estimated for all the physiological metrics as the above state. The error bar in Figure 6, shows the standard deviation and mean error square (MES) of the EDA in terms of the classified tonic and phasic responses. The standard deviation shows an average deviation from the mean response and the tonic and phasic change have an error rate of 0.1% and 0.2% from the mean and greater than the estimated value of 0.05% which is also similar to that of the EDA response. This result is feasible and shows the reliability of the model.

5 Conclusion

This paper demonstrates the use of pupil response and EDA to dynamic visual contents at the phasic level of the response reading, the paper integrates these two methods of eliciting the physiological response of a person by integrating the concepts of the two measures, thereby creating an analytical model for accessing both metrics as a form of multimodal physiological valuation of users

to dynamic contents of a webpage. The metric is integrated into a touch-sensor pad for recording the input image of the fingers and moisture content detection while they are involved in a task-allocated session. The two metrics were compared and errors in both physiological attributes were determined. The result shows less error in the contribution of EDA to cognitive stress detection to that of the pupil response and the authenticity of using EDA for stimulating the emotional response of users. The future perspective would be to use these metrics at an advanced level to determine basic stimuli that correlate to a response peak in real-time simulation. This would involve deriving a mathematical model that explicitly describes the multimodal phenomena and embraces the concepts of physiological modelling in the data description.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Nasarawa State University and Sheffield Hallam University for their contributions and sponsors of this paper.

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(a) Error in performance and contribution of pupil response based on classified tonic and phasic change for first set. (b) Error in performance and contribution of pupil response based on classified tonic and phasic change second set.

Figure 5: Performances based on error test.

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